

Abstract

In particle physics there exist two regions: the Standard Model which is fairly complete and the new physics sector which is completely unknown. In between and overlapping with both of these is neutrino physics. Neutrinos exist within the Standard Model but are not explained by it due to the discovery of neutrino oscillations. In this talk I will discuss where we stand with neutrino oscillations, where we might go with them, and how we might learn about the nature of neutrinos.

Modern Neutrino Oscillation Theory

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NuPhys KCL

January 7, 2026

Brookhaven[™]
National Laboratory

Absolute masses

Four known unknown in particle physics: all neutrinos

Atmospheric mass ordering

θ_{23} octant

Complex phase

Absolute mass scale

Atmospheric mass ordering

Mass ordering: what is it?

Normal

Inverted

Mass ordering: what is it really?

Requires the matter effect

Mass ordering current status: oscillations

1. NOvA and T2K both prefer **NO** over **IO**
2. NOvA+T2K prefers **IO** over **NO**
3. SK prefers **NO** over **IO** – statistics complicated
4. NOvA+T2K+SK still prefers **NO** over **IO**
5. + Daya Bay & RENO \Rightarrow slight preference **NO**
6. = no significant preference either way w/o SK; with SK $\sim 2\sigma$

PBD, J. Gehrlein, R. Pestes [2008.01110](#)
K. Kelly, et al. [2007.08526](#)
I. Esteban, et al. [2007.14792](#)
F. Capozzi, et al. [2107.00532](#)
P. de Salas, et al. [2006.11237](#)
I. Esteban, et al. [2410.05380](#)

Mass ordering current status: all

From oscillations:

Normal : $m_1 + m_2 + m_3 > 60$ meV Inverted : $m_1 + m_2 + m_3 > 100$ meV

Cosmology: $m_1 + m_2 + m_3 < 90$ meV at 95% CL

E. Valentino, S. Gariazzo, O. Mena [2106.15267](#)

→ 20 meV precision with DESI, EUCLID, ...

Pushing to very low (negative?) masses!?

N. Craig, et al. [2405.00836](#)

Many caveats: T. Bertólez-Martínez, et al. [2411.14524](#)

See also KATRIN [2406.13516](#)

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PRIORS?

Some claim “decisive” Bayesian evidence for normal

R. Jimenez, et al. [2203.14247](#)

More general prior assumptions ⇒ no significant information from cosmology

S. Gariazzo, et al. [1801.04946](#)

S. Gariazzo, et al. [2205.02195](#)

Mass ordering: future sensitivities

Joint
KM3NeT
JUNO

JUNO, KM3NeT [2108.06293](#)

JUNO, IceCube [1911.06745](#)

Note: if lower octant, KM3NeT is less sensitive

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$$\Delta m_{ee}^2 = c_{12}^2 \Delta m_{31}^2 + s_{12}^2 \Delta m_{32}^2$$

$$\Delta m_{\mu\mu}^2 = s_{12}^2 \Delta m_{31}^2 + c_{12}^2 \Delta m_{32}^2 + \mathcal{O}(s_{13} \Delta m_{21}^2)$$

Differ by $\pm \sim 1.1\%$ in each mass ordering

H. Nunokawa, S. Parke, R. Funchal [hep-ph/0503283](#)

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Matter effect \Rightarrow DUNE [2203.06100](#)

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Mass ordering: broad implications

- ▶ Affects cosmology
- ▶ Affects galactic SN signal
- ▶ Affects $0\nu\beta\beta$
- ▶ Affects flavor models
- ▶ Affects end point measurements
- ▶ Affects $C\nu B$

PBD, J. Gehrlein [2308.09737](#)

A. Long, C. Lunardini, E. Sabancilar [1405.7654](#)

Mass ordering: new physics degeneracies

In the presence of new physics such as NSI we have:

$$[\text{NO}] + [\epsilon = 0] \quad \equiv \quad [\text{IO}] + [\epsilon_{ee} = -2]$$

$$[\text{IO}] + [\epsilon = 0] \quad \equiv \quad [\text{NO}] + [\epsilon_{ee} = -2]$$

Equivalences hold even if all oscillation probabilities are *perfectly* measured

P. Bakhti, Y. Farzan [1403.0744](#)

P. Coloma, T. Schwetz [1604.05772](#)

P. Coloma, **PBD**, et al. [1701.04828](#)

PBD, S. Parke [2106.12436](#)

PBD, J. Gehrlein [2204.09060](#)

This is known as the **LMA-Dark** solution

Is the mass ordering robust?

Need **scattering** to break

Can probe same NC $\epsilon = -2$ process in scattering, but...

1. COHERENT for $M_{Z'} \gtrsim 50$ MeV and cosmology for $M_{Z'} \lesssim 5$ MeV

PBD, Y. Farzan, I. Shoemaker [1804.03660](#)

2. Reactor CEvNS for ϵ_{ee} for any mediator mass

PBD, J. Gehrlein [2204.09060](#)

3. Can still evade with specific flavor structures

$\epsilon_{\mu\mu} = \epsilon_{\tau\tau} = 2$ or certain u / d combinations

4. CCM & COHERENT can close all loopholes

θ_{23} octant

θ_{23} octant: what is it?

Normal

Inverted

θ_{23} octant: what is it really?

Lower octant more “normal” than upper octant

θ_{23} octant: current status

I. Esteban, et al. [2410.05380](#)

Upper/lower at $\sim 1\sigma$

F. Capozzi, et al. [2107.00532](#)

Prefers **lower** at $\sim 1.5\sigma$

P. de Salas, et al. [2006.11237](#)

Prefers **upper** at $> 2\sigma$

θ_{23} octant: future sensitivities

$\sim 3 - 5\sigma$

DUNE 2002.03005

$\sim 3 - 5\sigma$

HK 2505.15019

θ_{23} : broader implications

Normalcy

Is the heaviest neutrino mostly ν_τ ?

Is the lightest neutrino least ν_τ ?

Quarks easily satisfy normalcy [PBD 2003.04319](#)

μ - τ interchange/reflection symmetry

$$\nu_\mu \leftrightarrow \nu_\tau$$

$$M_\nu^* = X M_\nu X^T \quad X = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$M_\nu \equiv U D_\nu U^\dagger$$

Predicts: $\theta_{23} = 45^\circ$, often $\theta_{13} = 0$

P. Chen, et al. [1512.01551](#)

Parameter interplay

Models predict specific correlations among the parameters

Precision in all neutrino parameters is key!

Complex phase

δ and CP violation

$$J_{CP} = \Im(U_{e1}U_{\mu 2}U_{e2}^*U_{\mu 1}^*) = s_{12}c_{12}s_{13}c_{13}^2s_{23}c_{23} \sin \delta$$

C. Jarlskog [PRL 55, 1039 \(1985\)](#)

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C. Jarlskog [PRL 55, 1039 \(1985\)](#)

1. Strong interaction: no observed EDM \Rightarrow CP (nearly) **conserved**

$$\frac{\bar{\theta}}{2\pi} < 10^{-11}$$

J. Pendlebury, et al. [1509.04411](#)

2. Quark mass matrix: non-zero but **small** CP violation

$$\frac{|J_{CKM}|}{J_{\max}} = 3 \times 10^{-4}$$

CKMfitter [1501.05013](#)

3. Lepton mass matrix: ?

$$\frac{|J_{PMNS}|}{J_{\max}} < 0.34$$

[PBD](#), J. Gehrlein, R. Pestes [2008.01110](#)

$$J_{\max} = \frac{1}{6\sqrt{3}} \approx 0.096$$

δ : what is it really?

δ, J : current status

Maximal CP violation is already ruled out:

1. $\theta_{12} \neq 45^\circ$ at $\sim 15\sigma$
2. $\theta_{13} \neq \tan^{-1} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \approx 35^\circ$ at many (100) σ
3. $\theta_{23} = 45^\circ$ allowed at $\sim 1\sigma$
4. $|\sin \delta| = 1$ allowed

CP violation in oscillations

In vacuum at first maximum:

$$P_{\mu e} - \bar{P}_{\mu e} \approx 8\pi J \frac{\Delta m_{21}^2}{\Delta m_{32}^2}$$

- ▶ Extracting δ from data requires every other oscillation parameter
- ▶ J requires only Δm_{21}^2 (up to matter effects)
- ▶ Instead of asymmetry, can be determined via triple sine dependence

Matter effects in triple sine term can be accounted for

$$\hat{J} \simeq \frac{J}{\sqrt{(c_{212} - c_{13}^2 a / \Delta m_{21}^2)^2 + s_{212}^2} \sqrt{(c_{213} - a / \Delta m_{ee}^2)^2 + s_{213}^2}}$$

PBD, S. Parke [1902.07185](#)

PBD, H. Minakata, S. Parke [1604.08167](#)

When δ and when J ?

If the goal is **CP violation** the Jarlskog invariant should be used

however

If the goal is **measuring the parameters** one must use δ

Given θ_{12} , θ_{13} , θ_{23} , and J , I can't determine the sign of $\cos \delta$ which is physical

e.g. $P(\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_\mu)$ depends on $\cos \delta$
PBD 2309.03262

- ▶ T2K/HK are mostly sensitivity to $\sin \delta$; they should focus on J

T2K does this now!

- ▶ All LBL have modest $\cos \delta$ sensitivity; both J and δ should be reported

δ : future sensitivities

DUNE and HK will make great measurements via appearance $\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e$

$\nu + \bar{\nu}$ helps systematics but isn't strictly necessary

Need to know solar parameters to measure δ !

Current solar knowledge: okay

Future (JUNO): excellent

PBD, J. Gehrlein [2302.08513](#)

Impact of the true solar parameters on δ

Impact of the true solar parameters on δ

Non-standard CPV probes

1. Some information in solar due to loops in elastic scattering

V. Brdar, X-J. Xu [2306.03160](#)

K. Kelly, et al. [2407.03174](#) requires 3k Borexinos

2. Sub-GeV \rightarrow sub-100 MeV atmospheric

K. Kelly, et al. [1904.02751](#)

See also e.g. A. Suliga, J. Beacom [2306.11090](#)

Solar (no systematics)

Atmospherics at DUNE

Non-standard CPV probes: disappearance

Possible to get at CPV with CPC processes

Disappearance probability:

$$\begin{aligned}
 P(\nu_\alpha \rightarrow \nu_\alpha) = & 1 - 4|U_{\alpha 1}|^2|U_{\alpha 2}|^2 \sin^2 \Delta_{21} \\
 & - 4|U_{\alpha 1}|^2|U_{\alpha 3}|^2 \sin^2 \Delta_{31} \\
 & - 4|U_{\alpha 2}|^2|U_{\alpha 3}|^2 \sin^2 \Delta_{32} ,
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\Delta_{ij} = \Delta m_{ij}^2 L / 4E$$

Can measure all three coeffs of each frequency \Rightarrow 2 dofs
 δ (and CPV) needs 4 dofs \Rightarrow two dis measurements

ν_e : Daya Bay and KamLAND/JUNO

ν_μ : precision at DUNE/HK

Important cross check

Different and cleaner systematics than appearance

NuFast: Fast Neutrino Oscillation Probabilities

Result of a decade of work by Stephen Parke, myself, and others

Leverages *Eigenvector-Eigenvalue Identity*

PBD, S. Parke, T. Tao, X. Zhang [1908.03795](#)

Optimized to compute probabilities in three-flavor oscillations **fast**

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Optimized to compute probabilities in three-flavor oscillations **fast**

Long-baseline accelerator/reactor

github.com/PeterDenton/NuFast-LBL
Implemented in MaCh3, GUNDAM, ...

Atmospheric and nighttime solar

- ▶ Powerful caching feature. Changing some parameters is essentially free:
 - ▶ θ_{23}
 - ▶ δ
 - ▶ Production height
- ▶ Numerous Earth models implemented
- ▶ Orders of magnitude speedup

github.com/PeterDenton/NuFast-Earth
Experimental implementation in progress

New physics beyond standard three-flavor oscillations?

More new physics

Lots of neutrino anomalies and lots of ideas!

1. Gallium anomaly $\sim 5\sigma$ BEST [2109.11482](#)
 - ▶ No clear explanation PBD, H. Davoudiasl [2301.09651](#), V. Brdar, J. Gehrlein, J. Kopp [2303.05528](#),...
2. ANITA and KM3NeT's curious high energy events, 3σ , 5σ , and beyond
 - ▶ No clear explanation ANITA [1603.05218](#), KM3NeT [Nature \(2025\)](#)
3. LSND and MiniBooNE point to a ~ 1 eV sterile neutrino in appearance $\gtrsim 5\sigma$
 - ▶ Tension with cosmology, ν_μ disappearance, MicroBooNE LSND [hep-ex/0104049](#)
 - ▶ Many novel ideas such as heavier sterile that decays MiniBooNE [2006.16883](#)
 - ▶ Still testing at MicroBooNE, ICARUS, and SBND A. Abdullahi, et al. [2308.02543](#)
4. IceCube's ν_e/ν_μ ratio is energy dependent $\sim 3\sigma$ PBD, I. Tamborra [1805.05950](#)
 - ▶ Sources can only do so much, maybe neutrino decay? A. Abdullahi, [PBD 2005.07200](#)
5. NOvA and T2K seem to disagree on CPV $\sim 2\sigma$
 - ▶ Could be vector NSI PBD, J. Gehrlein, R. Pestes [2008.01110](#),...
6. Solar upturn? $\sim 2\sigma$
 - ▶ Could be vector NSI J. Liao, D. Marfatia, K. Whisnaut [1704.04711](#),...
 - ▶ Latest SuperK data indicates there may not be a problem

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Neutrino oscillation summary

- ▶ Four known unknowns in particle physics: all neutrinos
- ▶ Mass ordering will be measured (robustness?)
- ▶ θ_{23} octant is important for flavor models
- ▶ Multiple ways to determine CP violation: key cross check given systematics/BSM
- ▶ Rich new physics searches phenomenology!

Backups

References

SK [hep-ex/9807003](#)

M. Gonzalez-Garcia, et al. [hep-ph/0009350](#)

M. Maltoni, et al. [hep-ph/0207227](#)

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T. Schwetz, M. Tortola, J. Valle [0808.2016](#)

M. Gonzalez-Garcia, M. Maltoni, J. Salvado [1001.4524](#)

T2K [1106.2822](#)

D. Forero, M. Tortola, J. Valle [1205.4018](#)

D. Forero, M. Tortola, J. Valle [1405.7540](#)

P. de Salas, et al. [1708.01186](#)

F. Capozzi et al. [2003.08511](#)

The importance of $\cos \delta$

- ▶ If only $\sin \delta$ is measured \Rightarrow sign degeneracy: $\cos \delta = \pm\sqrt{1 - \sin^2 \delta}$
- ▶ Most flavor models predict $\cos \delta$

J. Gehrlein, et al. [2203.06219](#)

L. Everett, et al. [1912.10139](#)

δ : what is it not?

$\delta \not\Rightarrow$ Baryogenesis

The amount of leptogenesis is a function of:

1. δ
2. the heavy mass scale
3. α, β (Majorana phases)
4. CP phases in the RH neutrinos
5. ...

C. Hagedorn, et al. [1711.02866](#)

K. Moffat, et al. [1809.08251](#)

Measuring $\delta = 0, \pi$	$\not\Rightarrow$	no leptogenesis
Measuring $\delta \neq 0, \pi$	$\not\Rightarrow$	leptogenesis

Complex phase in different parameterizations

- ▶ Can relate the complex phase in one parameterization to that in another
- ▶ U_{132} and U_{213} similar to U_{123}
- ▶ δ constrained to $\sim [150^\circ, 210^\circ]$ in $U_{231}, U_{312}, U_{321}$
- ▶ Bands indicate 3σ uncertainty on $\theta_{12}, \theta_{13}, \theta_{23}$
- ▶ “50% of possible values of δ ”
 \Rightarrow parameterization dependent

DUNE TDR II [2002.03005](#)

Quark mixing

From the PDG, V_{CKM} in the V_{123} parameterization is

$$\theta_{12} = 13.09^\circ \quad \theta_{13} = 0.2068^\circ \quad \theta_{23} = 2.323^\circ \quad \delta_{\text{PDG}} = 68.53^\circ$$

Looks like “large” CPV:

$$\sin \delta_{\text{PDG}} = 0.93 \sim 1$$

yet $J_{\text{CKM}}/J_{\text{max}} = 3 \times 10^{-4}$.

Switch to V_{212} parameterization, $\Rightarrow \delta' = 1^\circ$ and $\sin \delta' = 0.02$.

Standard oscillation parameters

Can see that the combination doesn't like the NO while it does like the IO
IO preferred over NO at $\Delta\chi^2 = 2.3$

Repeated rotations

	U_{121}	U_{131}	U_{212}	U_{232}	U_{313}	U_{323}
$ U_{e2} $	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗
$ U_{e3} $	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓
$ U_{\mu 3} $	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓

Note that $e^{i\delta}$ must be on first or third rotation

Allowed δ' range

Many interesting new physics scenarios in oscillations

1. Sterile neutrinos
2. Non-standard neutrino interactions (NSI)
with any Lorentz structure: SPVAT
3. Non-standard neutrino self interactions
4. Neutrino decay
with visible or invisible final states
5. Unitarity violation
6. Many others: neutrino – dark matter interactions, environmental decoherence, and Lorentz invariance or CPT violation

Many interesting new physics scenarios in oscillations

1. Sterile neutrinos
[PBD, Y. Farzan, I. Shoemaker 1811.01310](#)
[PBD 2111.05793](#)
[H. Davoudiasl, PBD 2301.09651](#)
2. Non-standard neutrino interactions (NSI)
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[P. Coloma, PBD, et al. 1701.04828](#)
[PBD, J. Gehrlein, R. Pestes 2008.01110](#)
[PBD, J. Gehrlein 2008.06062](#), [2204.09060](#)
[PBD, A. Giarnetti, D. Meloni 2210.00109](#), [2409.15411](#)
3. Non-standard neutrino self interactions
[Barenboim, PBD, Oldengott 1903.02036](#)
4. Neutrino decay
with visible or invisible final states
[PBD, I. Tamborra 1805.05950](#)
[PBD, A. Abdullahi 2005.07200](#)
5. Unitarity violation
[PBD 2109.14576](#)
[PBD, J. Gehrlein 2109.14575](#)
6. Many others: neutrino – dark matter interactions, environmental decoherence,
and Lorentz invariance or CPT violation

See e.g. [PBD, J. Gehrlein, C.-F. Kong 2502.14027](#)

Shape-shifting sterile neutrinos

How to evade constraints?

Suppose:

1. Sterile neutrinos talk to dark matter

DM is ultralight boson

2. Dark matter talks to baryons

Then:

1. Sterile neutrinos aren't abundantly produced in the early universe
2. Mixing angle in the Sun is suppressed
3. Reactor constraints still exist

H. Davoudiasl, [PBD 2301.09651](#)
[PBD 2301.11106](#)

CP violation at NOvA and T2K?

Excitement at the Neutrino conference!

A. Himmel for NOvA [10.5281/zenodo.3959581](https://zenodo.org/record/3959581)

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{NSI}} = -2\sqrt{2}G_F \sum_{\alpha,\beta,f,P} \epsilon_{\alpha\beta}^{f,P} (\bar{\nu}_\alpha \gamma^\mu \nu_\beta) (\bar{f} \gamma_\mu f)$$

Models with large NSIs consistent with CLFV:

- Y. Farzan, I. Shoemaker [1512.09147](#) Y. Farzan, J. Heeck [1607.07616](#) D. Forero and W. Huang [1608.04719](#)
 K. Babu, A. Friedland, P. Machado, I. Mocioiu [1705.01822](#) **PBD**, Y. Farzan, I. Shoemaker [1804.03660](#)
 U. Dey, N. Nath, S. Sadhukhan [1804.05808](#) Y. Farzan [1912.09408](#) N. Bernal, Y. Farzan [2211.15686](#)
 S. Abbaslu, Y. Farzan [2407.13834](#)

Affects oscillations via new matter effect

$$H = \frac{1}{2E} \left[UM^2U^\dagger + a \begin{pmatrix} 1 + \epsilon_{ee} & \epsilon_{e\mu} & \epsilon_{e\tau} \\ \epsilon_{e\mu}^* & \epsilon_{\mu\mu} & \epsilon_{\mu\tau} \\ \epsilon_{e\tau}^* & \epsilon_{\mu\tau}^* & \epsilon_{\tau\tau} \end{pmatrix} \right]$$

Matter potential $a \propto G_F \rho E$

B. Dev, K. Babu, **PBD**, P. Machado, et al. [1907.00991](#)

Estimate size of effect: magnitude

$$|\epsilon_{e\beta}| \approx \frac{s_{12}c_{12}c_{23}\pi\Delta m_{21}^2}{2s_{23}w_\beta} \left| \frac{\sin \delta_{\text{T2K}} - \sin \delta_{\text{NOvA}}}{a_{\text{NOvA}} - a_{\text{T2K}}} \right| \approx \begin{cases} 0.22 & \text{for } \beta = \mu \\ 0.24 & \text{for } \beta = \tau \end{cases}$$

$$a \propto \rho E$$

$$w_\beta = s_{23}, c_{23} \text{ for } \beta = \mu, \tau$$

Assumed upper octant $\theta_{23} > 45^\circ$

Consistency checks:

- ▶ $\sin \delta_{\text{NOvA}} = \sin \delta_{\text{T2K}} \Rightarrow |\epsilon| = 0$
- ▶ $\sin \delta_{\text{NOvA}} \neq \sin \delta_{\text{T2K}}$ and $a_{\text{NOvA}} = a_{\text{T2K}} \Rightarrow |\epsilon| \rightarrow \infty$
- ▶ Octant:
 1. LBL is governed by ν_3
 2. Upper octant $\Rightarrow \nu_3$ is more ν_μ
 3. More $\nu_\mu \Rightarrow$ need less new physics coupling to ν_μ to produce a given effect

NSI parameters

Orange is preferred over SM at integer values of $\Delta\chi^2$, dark gray is disfavored at 4.61

T. Ehrhardt, IceCube [PPNT \(2019\)](#)

$\epsilon_{\mu\tau}$, IO in backups

Other CP violating NSI constraints

NSI effects grow with energy, density, and distance

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Best probes:

- ▶ $\epsilon_{\mu\tau}$: atmospheric
- ▶ $\epsilon_{e\mu}, \epsilon_{e\tau}$: LBL appearance, atmospheric
- ▶ IceCube
 - ▶ Constraint is at LBL best fit with 3 yrs
10 yrs of data in the bank
 - ▶ Prefers non-zero $|\epsilon_{e\mu}|$ at $\sim 1\sigma$

T. Ehrhardt, IceCube [PPNT \(2019\)](#)

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- ▶ Super-K
 - ▶ Only consider real NSI
 - ▶ Comparable sensitivity as IceCube

- ▶ COHERENT
 - ▶ Only applies to NSI models with $M_{Z'} \gtrsim 10$ MeV
 - ▶ NSI u , d , e configuration matters
 - ▶ Comparable constraints

T. Ehrhardt, IceCube [PPNT \(2019\)](#)

Super-K [1109.1889](#)

COHERENT [1708.01294](#)

[PBD](#), Y. Farzan, I. Shoemaker [1804.03660](#)

[PBD](#), J. Gehrlein [2008.06062](#)

Unitarity violation: a tale of two regimes

*Details depends on the specific experiment/channel

Unitarity violation: how to calculate

Kinematically **accessible** states

1. Unitary calculation of full $n \times n$ matrix
2. Oscillation averaged:

$$\sin^2 \frac{\Delta m_{41}^2 L}{4E} \rightarrow \frac{1}{2}$$

$$\sin \frac{\Delta m_{41}^2 L}{4E} \rightarrow 0$$

3. No matter effect:

$$H^{\text{mat}} = \text{diag}(V_{\text{CC}} + V_{\text{NC}}, V_{\text{NC}}, V_{\text{NC}}, 0, \dots)$$

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Kinematically **inaccessible** states

1. Nonunitary calculation of $m \times m$ matrix
 $m =$ number of kinematically accessible states
2. Rescale probability:

$$P_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{|\sum_{i=1}^{\text{acc}} U_{\alpha i}^* e^{iP_i L} U_{\beta i}|}{(\sum_{i=1}^{\text{acc}} U_{\alpha i}^* U_{\alpha i})(\sum_{i=1}^{\text{acc}} U_{\beta i}^* U_{\beta i})}$$

3. Cannot subtract multiples of $\mathbb{1}$
4. Rescale cross section/flux as appropriate
5. Rescale G_F in matter effect

Unitarity violation status from oscillations

3σ maximal deviations from unitarity

	Leptons	
	Hu+	Ellis+
ν_e row	0.003	0.05
ν_μ row	0.02	0.04
ν_τ row	0.2	0.82
ν_1 col	0.06	0.22
ν_2 col	0.09	0.27
ν_3 col	0.12	0.40

	Quarks	
	u row	0.0015 $\sim 2.2\sigma$ tension
c row	0.06	
t row	-	
d col	0.005	
s col	0.06	
b col	-	

Lepton constraints don't include anomalies

Care is required

S. Ellis, K. Kelly, S. Li [2008.01088](#)

Z. Hu, et al. [2008.09730](#)

S. Parke, M. Ross-Lonergan [1508.05095](#)

PDG

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Vastly different mixing angle hierarchy

\Rightarrow

Like comparing apples and steak

S. Ellis, K. Kelly, S. Li [2008.01088](#)

Z. Hu, et al. [2008.09730](#)

S. Parke, M. Ross-Lonergan [1508.05095](#)

PDG

Unitarity violation: tau row

Leptons: tau row is the weakest

1. Existing global analyses use OPERA and SNO
2. More data from atmospheric ν_τ appearance!

Also astrophysical ν_τ appearance; weak but distinct!

Atmospheric works because τ is in **direct** region

PBD, et al. [2203.05591](#)

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Tau neutrino data set doubles every two years!

PBD, et al. [2203.05591](#)

Unitarity violation

Consistency of the three-flavor oscillation picture?

and/or

Searches for unitarity violation?

Unitarity violation

Consistency of the three-flavor oscillation picture?

and/or

Searches for unitarity violation?

Not the same!

Lots of models to test standard three-flavor picture:
Sterile, unitarity violation, NSI, neutrino decay, decoherence, ...

Unitarity violation: what is it?

Our 3×3 matrix isn't unitary:

$$U_3 U_3^\dagger \neq \mathbb{1}$$

Addition of new flavor states $\nu_a, \nu_b, \nu_c, \dots$ and new mass states ν_4, ν_5, ν_6

$$U \rightarrow \begin{pmatrix} U_{e1} & U_{e2} & U_{e3} & U_{e4} & \cdots \\ U_{\mu1} & U_{\mu2} & U_{\mu3} & U_{\mu4} & \cdots \\ U_{\tau1} & U_{\tau2} & U_{\tau3} & U_{\tau4} & \cdots \\ U_{a1} & U_{a2} & U_{a3} & U_{a4} & \cdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots \end{pmatrix}$$

Unitarity Violation \Rightarrow

New mass states not directly accessible by oscillations or decay

Thus check if U_3 is what it should be

Unitarity constraints

Unitary violation: the study of how $U_{3\times 3}$ is not unitary independent of m_4, m_5, \dots
Constraints vary considerably in the literature:

$$1 - |U_{e1}|^2 - |U_{e2}|^2 - |U_{e3}|^2 < \begin{cases} 0.05 \\ 0.001 \end{cases} \quad \text{at } 2\sigma$$

S. Parke, M. Ross-Lonergan [1508.05095](#)

Z. Hu, et al. [2008.09730](#)

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All analyses *assume* unitarity
Throw out LSND, MiniBooNE, RAA, gallium, etc.

S. Parke, M. Ross-Lonergan [1508.05095](#)

Z. Hu, et al. [2008.09730](#)

Unitarity violation

- ▶ Could conceivably differentiate: 2 new states from 1, but not 3+ from 2

- ▶ Zero distance effect \Rightarrow near detector **with flux prediction**

E.g. RAA, Gallium

- ▶ Numerous parameterizations: α matrix, η matrix, submatrix & Cauchy-Schwartz

All apply to the inaccessible cases only

- ▶ There is an approximate correspondence to sterile and NSI

$$\alpha_{ee} \approx \frac{1}{2}(s_{14}^2 + s_{15}^2 + s_{16}^2) \approx -\epsilon_{ee}, \quad \dots$$

M. Blennow, et al. [1609.08637](#)

Applies one experiment at a time

- ▶ Additional EW precision information: W, Z, π , μ , τ decays

Care is required

S. Antusch, et al. [hep-ph/0607020](#)

S. Antusch, O. Fischer [1407.6607](#)

Unitarity violation: mass ranges for tau neutrinos

experiment	(4,4) (m_4)	(5,3) (m_4)
atmospheric ν_μ disappearance	$\in [10 \text{ eV}, 15 \text{ MeV}]$	$\gtrsim 40 \text{ MeV}$
atmospheric ν_τ appearance	$\in [10 \text{ eV}, 15 \text{ MeV}]$	$\gtrsim 40 \text{ MeV}$
astrophysical ν_τ appearance	$\lesssim 15 \text{ MeV}$	$\gtrsim 40 \text{ MeV}$
solar ^8B	$\lesssim 5 \text{ MeV}$	$\gtrsim 20 \text{ MeV}$
DONuT/FASERnu	$\in [100 \text{ eV}, 90 \text{ MeV}]$	$\gtrsim 200 \text{ MeV}$
LBL ν_τ appearance (OPERA)	$\in [1 \text{ eV}, 15 \text{ MeV}]$	$\gtrsim 40 \text{ MeV}$
LBL ν_τ appearance (DUNE)	$\in [0.1 \text{ eV}, 15 \text{ MeV}]$	$\gtrsim 40 \text{ MeV}$
LBL ν_μ disappearance (DUNE)	$\in [0.1 \text{ eV}, 15 \text{ MeV}]$	$\gtrsim 40 \text{ MeV}$
CEvNS	$\in [10 \text{ eV}, 15 \text{ MeV}]$	$\gtrsim 40 \text{ MeV}$

PBD, J. Gehrlein [2109.14575](#)

CP violation discovery with disappearance

Need JUNO and either DUNE or HK

PBD 2309.03262